

Examining Factors that Motivate Individuals to Participate in the Amplification of Disinformation through Facebook

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Abstract

It is one of the most dangerous weapons in existence. It has been utilized in various ways since the analog era. Now that life has turned digital, the need to fit in and maintain its status as one of the great weapons to achieve specific goals. The digital transformation of life has led to social media playing a vast role, among which is Facebook. Facebook is ranked as the most rapidly growing social media platform, boasting a vast number of subscribers. Thus, this study aims to identify the factors that influence the use of social media platforms, using Facebook as a case study. It also statistically explores the relationship between factors influencing involvement on Facebook. In addition, it suggests some recommendations for diminishing through Facebook, and it seems to be an initial investigation into the role of social media, with Facebook as a case study. This study examined the potential factors that influence involvement on Facebook, statistically analyzing the relationship between these factors and providing recommendations for Facebook. It proposes a model of the factors that influence the use of Facebook social media. The model was analyzed using empirical or statistical analysis. The data were collected through two different questionnaire survey responses: one online distribution. The survey was conducted in July – August 2025, with 207 responses. The results of the proposed model analysis suggest that political attitude, financial gains, religious violence, ethnic/tribal conflict, and entertainment are the essential factors that influence the use of Facebook. Theoretically, this study provides a fresh contribution to understanding and factors that it fills a gap in the literature

Keywords:

Facebook, Disinformation, Amplification, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

According to some perspectives, weaponizing is as old as the world itself. Satan uses a weapon to aid in Adam and Eve's disobedience to God, which results in their being cast down to earth as punishment. It was mentioned that Satan spread to them by telling them to eat the fruit of the forbidden tree, which made them knowledgeable and allowed them to live young for an extended period. Since then, has been used right before using text in the entire world as a severe verbal weapon to achieve specific goals by some individuals. It has reached a stage that those who are good at creating against some individual or group are given special consideration, respect, and are given special status in the palaces, for they can use them for the rulers' interest. On Nigeria's social media, a type of false information that consists of deliberate misinformation or hoaxes is spread via online social media. is written and published to mislead and positively or negatively impact an agency, entity, or person, often using sensationalist, dishonest, or outright fabricated headlines to increase readership, online sharing, and Internet click revenue.

The use of social media can have a positive impact, such as when a government or an agency will at times decide to come up with a new strategy that might not be favorable to society. Some members of society can choose to weaponize on a social media platform to make government agencies act in favor of the community members, either economically, socially, morally, financially,

academically, or politically. After solving a severe problem, such as a community quarrel or war, it can be publicized on social media, such as Facebook, to make community members more focused and keep them alert.

The use of social media platforms can negatively impact an individual, or a politician can decide to weaponize a fabricated story against an opponent politician to him or to create hatred against that very politician. On a social media platform, information can be weaponized against an environment or community by attaching some pictures that might not even be from the country or very old photos of an immense tragedy, to blackmail them or create a faction between that community and another community to achieve financial, economic, social, political, ethical, or moral benefits. Thus, this study intends to identify the factors that influence the use of social media and recommend some ways of using Facebook as a case study.

The use of social media platforms in Nigeria affects many sectors, such as economic, security, social, political, financial/business, academic, and other sectors in the country. Social media has doubtlessly become a powerful tool for organizing and mobilizing massive groups of like-minded individuals through different channels, such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, WhatsApp, and many others. For instance, an article was recently released by Tabia Princewell Vanguard newspaper dated February 28, 2018, stating that it was recently brought to her attention that a newspaper, in a report on the Depchi Kidnappings, used a friend's picture to illustrate the story. The young woman is neither a student nor a relative of any of the students, nor does she have anything to do with the girls' school. Her picture was simply taken off her social media page and used as an illustration for the report for unfathomable reasons. We must remember the numerous instances where Nigerian media outlets mistakenly but often portray South Sudanese rebels, armed and tending cattle, as the violent herdsmen currently attacking communities in the Middle Belt. It took a few days before anyone could ascertain whether General Ibrahim Babangida had indeed authorized the recent letter written by his media, due to the denials and counter-denials published by the media. This confusion was caused by the Yobe state government initially releasing facts that it said

were obtained from the Nigerian Army, claiming the latter had recovered the kidnapped Dapchi girls. It later had to release another embarrassing, apologetic statement, admitting that the information provided by the Army was false. Chaos and misstatements have become the mainstay of public authorities and media organizations in Nigeria. It is sometimes difficult to separate fact from fiction in the digital age, but Nigeria has taken this trend to the extreme. All these are types that are being transmitted digitally, especially on Facebook, which is beyond the control of any individual or government as a whole.

Therefore, this study aims to identify the factors (i.e., political, financial, religious, ethnic/tribal, and entertainment/fun) influencing engagement in the field, and statistically explore the relationship between these factors and the use of social media. Finally, recommendations on how to mitigate the threat through social media platforms in Nigeria are provided.

2. Literature Review

This section dwells on the conceptual framework that examines 's on social media platforms, but strictly Facebook. The essential required tools and variables are explained here with their definitions and possible subjects. According to many understandings, the term has no single definite meaning, but there are many definitions. Hoax news refers to false information or propaganda published under the guise of authentic news (Stroud, 2017). is made-up stuff, masterfully manipulated to look like credible journalistic reports that are easily spread online to large audiences willing to believe the fictions and spread the word. (PolitiFact 2017). is a type of yellow journalism or propaganda that consists of deliberate misinformation or hoaxes spread via traditional print and broadcast news media or online social media. (Leonhardt, David; Thompson, Stuart A. June 23, 2017). Stories that appear to be news, spread on the internet, or using other media, are usually created to influence political views or as a joke. (Cambridge University Press). is written and published with the intent to mislead or damage an agency, entity, or person, or gain financially or politically. (Hunt, Elle, December 17, 2016). This false information is mainly distributed by social media and is periodically circulated through

mainstream media. (Himma-Kadaas, Marju, July 2017).

The term is used in this context to show the level of severity of the deadly way that has been used on social media platforms, specifically Facebook, to achieve specific goals or objectives. Social media is a form of electronic communication (such as) through which online communities are created to share information, ideas, personal messages, etc. (Dictionary and Thesaurus Merriam-Webster 2016). (Dictionary social media is also an essential source of news. According to 'Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2013', social media are among the most important ways to find online (the others being traditional brands, search engines, and news aggregators) (Newman, N.; Levy, D. 2013). Social media are computer-mediated technologies that facilitate the creation and sharing of information, ideas, career interests, and other forms of expression via virtual communities and networks. (Obar, Jonathan A.; Wildman, Steve, 2015). Users typically access social media services via web-based technologies on desktops, laptops, or download services that offer social media functionality to their mobile devices (e.g., smartphones and tablet computers). When engaging with these services, users can create highly interactive platforms through which individuals, communities, and organizations can share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated or pre-made content posted online. They "introduce substantial and pervasive changes to communication between organizations, communities, and individuals. (Kietzmann, Jan H.; Kristopher Hemkens, 2011). Social media differ from paper-based media (e.g., magazines and newspapers) to traditional electronic media such as TV broadcasting in many ways, including quality, reach, frequency, interactivity, usability, immediacy, and performance. (Agichtein, Eugene; Carlos Castillo.) Debora Donato; Aristides Gionis; Gilad Mishne 2008). Social media outlets operate in a dialogic transmission system (many sources to many receivers). (Agichtein, Eugene; Carlos Castillo.) Debora Donato; Aristides Gionis; Gilad Mishne 2008). This is in contrast to traditional media, which operates under a monologic transmission model (one source to many receivers), such as a newspaper delivered to many subscribers or a radio station that broadcasts the same programs to an entire city. Many social media

Facebook, Google+, Myspace, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Snapchat, Twitter, Viber, WeChat, WhatsApp, and Wikia. In this context, we are more concerned with Facebook, which is the scope and limit of my project.

Facebook is an American online social media and social networking service company based in Menlo Park, California. Its website was launched on February 4, 2004, by Mark Zuckerberg and fellow Harvard College students and roommates Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz, and Chris Hughes. The founders initially limited the website's membership to Harvard students. Later, they expanded it to higher education institutions in the Boston area, Ivy League schools, and Stanford University. Facebook gradually added support for students at various universities and eventually for high school students. Since 2006, anyone who claims to be at least 13 years old has been allowed to become a registered user of Facebook, although variations exist in this requirement depending on local laws. The name comes from the directories often given to American university students. Facebook held its initial public offering (IPO) in February 2012, valuing the company at \$104 billion, the highest valuation to date for a newly listed public company. It began selling stocks to the public three months later. Facebook generates most of its revenue from onscreen advertisements. Facebook can be accessed from many devices with Internet connectivity, such as desktop computers, laptops, tablet computers, and smartphones. After registering, users can create a customized profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended, etc. Users can add other users as "friends," exchange messages, post status updates, share photos, videos, and links, use various software applications ("apps"), and receive notifications of other users' activities.

Additionally, users may join common-interest user groups organized by workplace, school, hobbies, or other topics, and categorize their friends into lists such as "From Work" or "Close Friends." Additionally, users can report or block unpleasant. Facebook had more than 2.2 billion monthly active users as of January 2018. Its popularity has led to prominent media coverage of the company, including significant scrutiny of privacy and psychological effects. In recent years, the company has faced intense pressure over the amount of hate speech and depictions of violence prevalent on its

services, all of which it is attempting to counteract. In October 2016, Facebook announced a fee-based communications tool called Workplace that aims to "connect everyone" while at work. Users can create profiles, see updates from co-workers on their news feeds, stream live videos, and participate in secure group chats. (Hu, Howard; October 11, 2016). Facebook enables users to choose their privacy settings and choose who can see specific parts of their profile. The website is free for its users and generates revenue from advertising, such as banner ads. (Barton, Zoe; April 28, 2006) Facebook requires a user's name and profile picture (if applicable) to be accessible to everyone. Users can control who sees other information they have shared and find them in searches through their privacy settings. On the issue of combating January 21, 2015, Facebook's algorithm is programmed to filter out false or misleading content, such as stories and hoaxes, and will be supported by users who select the option to flag a word as "purposefully fake or deceitful news." According to Reuters, such content is "being spread like wildfire" on social media platforms. Facebook maintained that "satirical" content, "intended to be humorous, or content that is clearly labeled as satire," will be taken into account and should not be intercepted. (Oreskovic, Alexei; January 20, 2015) The algorithm, however, has been accused of maintaining a "filter bubble," where both material the user disagrees with (Bakshy, Eytan; Messing, Solomon; Adamic, Lada A.; June 5, 2015) and posts with a low number of likes will also not be seen. (Unicorn Booty; 2015) In November 2015, Zuckerberg prolonged a period of paternity leave from 4 weeks to 4 months. (Gong; November 28, 2015). This indicates that Facebook's entire discourse is disrupted by the way it has been weaponized on the Facebook social media platform.

Political Attitude: - Is Political attitude one of the significant influences on social media, specifically Facebook. In this study, I will go with the definition of Balmas (2014), who divides political attitude into three (3) categories: political efficacy, political alienation, and political cynicism. Political efficacy can be divided into internal political effectiveness and external political efficacy (Niemi, Craig, & Mattei, 1991). Internal political efficacy can be defined as "beliefs about one's competence to understand, and to participate effectively in politics." In contrast, external political efficacy is

defined as "beliefs about the responsiveness of governmental authorities and institutions to citizen demands" (Niemi et al., 1991, pp. 1407-1408). These constructs shape the overall political efficacy. Finifter (1970) defined political alienation as a consolidated feeling of not being able to affect politics, a sense that political decisions are unpredictable, the absence of political regulation, and the rejection of political norms and goals. Lastly, political cynicism is defined as "the belief that politicians care more about self-interest than about ordinary and more about retaining their positions than the best interests of the country" (Balmas, 2014, pp. 437). In short, political attitudes are defined as attitudes towards someone's political competence, the government, politicians, and the political system.

Financial Gain: Some engaged in the act to extort money from others. This can be achieved through blackmail, extortion, or lies to take advantage of the target victim. The amount of monetary gain (earned or unearned) accruing over a given period is also a significant factor influencing the amount of engagement on social media platforms.

Religious Violence: This term covers phenomena where religion is either the subject or the object of violent behavior. (Wellman, James; Tokuno, Kyoko, 2004) Religious Violence is, precisely, Violence that is motivated by or in reaction to religious precepts, texts, or doctrines. This includes violence against religious institutions, objects, or events when the violence is motivated to some degree by some religious aspect of the target or by the attacker's precepts. Religious Violence does not refer exclusively to religious groups' acts but includes acts committed by secular groups against religious groups.

Ethnic conflict: A conflict between two or more contending ethnic groups. While the source of the conflict may be political, social, economic, or religious, the individuals in conflict must expressly fight for their ethnic group's position within society. This final criterion differentiates ethnic conflicts from other forms of struggle. (Varshney, Ashutosh 2002) (Kaufman, Stuart J. 2001).

Entertainment: Is a form of activity that holds the attention and interest of an audience or gives pleasure and delight. It can be an idea or a task, but

is more likely to be one of the activities or events that have developed over thousands of years to keep an audience's attention. (William Caxton).

3. Research Methodology

To achieve the main objective of this study, the most suitable research design and methods are required. The current phenomenon under investigation, the research objectives, the selected research area, and the respondents for this research primarily influenced the approach's selection, followed by the research questions (Sekaran, 2003). The specific objectives of this study were as follows:

- To identify factors influencing to engage in the of through Facebook.
- To statistically explore the relationship between factors influencing engagement in social media (e.g., Facebook).
- To provide recommendations on how to diminish the use of social media in Nigeria.

Research Instrument

The instrument for this research was developed to collect data about the phenomenon of Facebook, which is the deliberate attempt to share/create misinformation via social media platforms such as Facebook. It intends to mislead, interrupt, insult, and disorganize to gain political influence, financial gain, religious conflict, ethnic/tribal conflict, and entertainment for fun. The questionnaire consisted of three sections: (A) demographic questions; (B) use of questions; and (C) factors influencing. It was administered in two ways: face-to-face administration to respondents and online distribution.

Population and Sample

This research population includes different political attitudes, other financial interests, different religious beliefs, different /tribes, and various entertainment reasons, of which some are direct respondents, and some are those who responded online. A sufficient number of users were sampled to meet the minimum satisfactory sample size required to conduct the empirical survey. Two separate surveys were conducted in this project: first, a questionnaire survey of social media users, specifically Facebook, to explore the motives behind weaponizing on social media platforms, specifically Facebook; and second, a questionnaire

survey of 100 direct respondents to also explore on social media platforms using Facebook as a case study. Thus, a total of 207 respondents with knowledge of using the Facebook social media platform participated in this study, which was considered sufficient to meet the sample size requirement for conducting factor analysis (Chin, 1998; Gefen al., 2000; Kim, Oh, Shin, and Chae, 2009).

Sampling

The questionnaire survey was conducted among individuals with different political attitudes, other financial gain, different religious beliefs, different tribes, and various entertainment reasons at other locations using the sampling technique from July to August of 2018. The questionnaire was administered in two ways: on one of my Facebook pages and directly to the respondents. Phone calls to some online and direct respondents were made, and the researchers politely aided in the quick completion of the questionnaire. Thus, phone calls helped increase the response rate. The researcher sufficiently explained the purpose of the research to some respondents and guided some respondents by completing the survey where necessary.

4.Data Analysis

This section presents the statistical analysis of the use of social media platforms, specifically Facebook. The section is organized in the following sequence: first, the descriptive analysis of the respondents' profiles; second, a basic understanding of Facebook; third, an analysis of the factors influencing is subdivided into five categories: political attitude, financial gain, religious violence, ethnic conflict, and entertainment, which are considered the most prevalent factors and encompass all other factors that influence of on social media platforms, specifically Facebook.

Descriptive Data Analysis of the Profiles

To collect useful and accurate responses to answer the research questions, the sample must represent the population (Sekaran, 2003). Therefore, relevant demographic data were requested from the survey participants. Generally, the respondents' data distribution appears to represent the population, as described in this section.

A total of 207 responses to the survey were initially received, 127 and 80 from one-on-one and online

respondents, respectively, with the help of Google doc, respectively. A data screening analysis was conducted on both the one-on-one and online responses before the primary data analysis began for three reasons: (a) to ensure the accuracy of the data collected; (b) to deal with missing data; and (c) to deal with extreme cases. To eliminate these three problems, a physical examination of each returned questionnaire was performed; 27 questionnaires were dropped from one respondent, and two responses from online responses were dropped due to either missing data or careless responses. One hundred seventy-eight (178) responses were retained for further analysis. In this section of the questionnaire, six questions were asked regarding the respondents' characteristics, as shown in Table 1.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows that the majority of the aged are 50 years or above (N=91, 51%), followed by 30–39years (N=74, 42%), and then and above (N=12, 7%). In the gender section, 127 respondents were male, while 51 were female (71% and 29%,

respectively. The majority of the respondents were BSC/HND holders (N=85, 48%), followed by NCE/ND (N=45, 25%), PG/Masters (N=42, 24%), and finally SSCE/NECO (N=6, 3%). The majority of the respondents owned at least one Facebook account (N=176, 99%); only a negligible number (N=2, 1%) did not. The proficiency in Facebook use is very important for this study. All the respondents indicated that they use Facebook every day, spending adequate time on Facebook surfing, with the majority spending 2 hours and above (N=55, 31%) than those that spend about 31 – 60 minutes (N=51, 29%), followed by those that spend about 1 – 2 hours (N=45, 21%), and finally those that spend about 0 – 30 minutes (N=26, 15%). The most regular activity on Facebook from the findings was reading news feeds (N=133, 75%), followed by chat/sending messages (N=105, 59%), checking/posting pictures (N=76, 43%), and posting/watching videos (N=58, 33%).

Table 1: descriptive analysis

Demographic characteristics		Online	1 on 1	%
Age	18yrs to 29yrs	11	80	51%
	30yrs to 39yrs	59	15	42%
	40yrs and above	7	5	7%
Gender	Male	67	60	71%
	Female	11	40	29%
Educational level	SSCE/NECO	1	5	3%
	NCE/ND	5	40	25%
	BSC/HND	35	50	48%
	PG/Masters	37	5	24%
Owning a Facebook account	Yes	76	100	99%
	No	2		1%
Time on	0 – 30min	16	10	15%
	31min – 60min	26	25	29%
	1hr – 2hrs	10	35	25%
	2hrs and above	25	30	31%
Regular activities on Facebook (multiple choice allowed)	Check/post pictures	46	30	43%
	Chat/send messages	45	60	59%
	Read news feed	63	70	75%
	Post/Watch Videos	33	25	33%

Analysis of the Knowledge on Facebook

The most important part of this study was collecting respondents' perceptions based on their previous experience of fabrication on Facebook. As such, respondents were asked to present the little

they knew about the term using four scales of measurement that strongly agree disagree, and strongly disagree. The four scales of measurement here are classified into two: strongly agree/agree with the positive impact and the level at which

support the term, while strongly disagree with the negative impact and the level at which rebel from the statement. Table 2 illustrates the possible level at which information can be passed through Facebook, where the majority of the respondents believe that fact (96%), and those who disagree only (4%). This shows that almost all the respondents agreed that it could be passed through Facebook. Also, (90%) of respondents believed that it could be used as a weapon on Facebook, where only (10%) disagree, which might be a negligible number. (67%) of the respondents that government is responsible for identifying on Facebook social media platform 33% of the government is responsible for determining on Facebook. It might be possible that they were thinking of other sources of identification on Facebook. Also, 73% of respondents believe that the general

public was responsible for identifying on a social media platform, and 27% disagree. From the findings here, respondents think the general public is more responsible for identifying on Facebook than the government. Social media platform owners might be responsible for identifying on Facebook, having 74% and 26%. On the aspect of a private organization (e.g., NGOs), the agreed response was low (58%), though higher than (42%) private organizations. In a nutshell, after passing through Facebook and using it as a weapon, identifying on Facebook social media is a joint task among the government, the general public, social media platforms, and private organizations, though social media platforms had the highest responses (74%) on this section.

Table 2: Knowledge about the term on Facebook

Please indicate the extent to which the following	Agree	Disagree
Do you think it can be passed through Facebook?	96%	4%
Do you think it can be used on Facebook as a weapon?	90%	10%
The government is responsible for identifying on social media	67%	33%
The general public is responsible for identifying on social media	73%	27%
The social media is responsible for identifying on social media	74%	26%
Private organizations (e.g., NGO's) are responsible for identifying on social media	58%	42%

Analysis of the Factors Influencing

This section statistically analyzes the most important and most popular factors that influence the fabrication on Facebook social media. The present analysis of the results of the factors influencing. The factors are political attitude, financial gain, religious violence, ethnic/tribal conflict, and entertainment.

Table 3 presents the statistical analyses of political Attitude as a factor that influences fabrication on social media platforms. Both the online responses and one response were presented in 3. Political attitude responses were up to (94%), which indicates the respondents believe over the fact that political Attitude might be a very strong factor in the fabrication of content on Facebook. Having only 6% of respondents disagree, which might be considered a negligible response. (82%) Some of the responses indicate that social media can have a

positive influence on the political career of an individual having just (18%) responses. Therefore, the positive reaction is higher than the negative reaction. On Facebook can influence on a political career negatively received (87%), with only (13%) disagree response; the result here can have both positive and negative influences on a political career, with (82%) and (87%) respectively. An (84%) response goes to the fact that can be fabricated on Facebook against the government to achieve some individual objectives, having just (16%) disagree responses, which signify the respondent's level of agreement. Mitigating the fabrication of on Facebook can help put the political system into order having (81%) and disagree responses had just (19%). In a nutshell, political Attitude can be mentioned as one of the greatest and most powerful factors that influence fabrication through the Facebook social media platform, having the highest percentage of (94%).

Table 3: Political Attitude as a factor

Please indicate the extent to which political influence	Agree	Disagree
Political Attitude is a factor that influences the fabrication on Facebook	94%	6%
On Facebook, social media can have a positive influence on the Political career of an individual	82%	18%
On Facebook can influence a political career negatively	87%	13%
can be fabricated on Facebook against the government to achieve some specific objectives	84%	16%
Mitigating the fabrication on Facebook can assist in putting the political system in order	81%	19%

Table 4 presents the statistical analyses of financial Gain as a factor that influences fabrication on social media platforms. The Table shows that the response of (87%) shows that financial Gain can be achieved on Facebook, with just (14%) responses. (67%) indicate that on Facebook can increase an individual's financial income, while a good percentage, up to (33%) disagree with the assertion. (75%) Indicating on Facebook can affect an individual's financial income having (25%) disagree. (78%) agreed that could be used on

Facebook to manipulate money from either organization or individuals having (22%) disagree. Mitigating fabrication of on Facebook can assist in saving the financial institution or individuals from financial crimes got just (51%) very close to the disagree responses of (49%); the difference here clearly shows that a good number of respondents didn't agree, they might be thinking of other sources of mitigating fabrication of on Facebook to affect financial institutions of individuals.

Table 4: Financial Gain as a factor

Please indicate the extent to which financial Gain	Agree	Disagree
Financial Gain can be fabricated on Facebook	87%	14%
On Facebook, an individual can increase their financial income of an individual	67%	33%
On Facebook can affect the financial income of an individual	75%	25%
can be used on Facebook to manipulate money from either an individual	78%	22%
Mitigating fabrication on Facebook can assist in saving the financial institution or individual from financial crimes	51%	49%

Table 5 presents the statistical analyses of religious Violence as a factor that influences fabrication on social media platforms. Religion can be used as a means of fabrication on Facebook, having an agreed response (86%) with just (14%) disagree responses. (86%) agreed that Facebook could create religious conflict among (14%). On Facebook, some religious beliefs, having (84%) on responses,

and just (16%). (93%) Respondents agree that it can be fabricated on Facebook against different religious groups or societies/sects, with just (7%), respondents, which might be considered negligible. It is part of the biggest problem we currently have in Nigeria. (83%) Respondents agreed that Fabrication could assist individuals or society against religious Violence with (17%) responses. In

a nutshell, religious conflict is a decisive factor that influences the fabrication on the Facebook social

media platform. A response of (93%) can be fabricated on Facebook against different religious groups or societies/ sects.

Table 5: Religious Violence as a Factor

Please indicate the extent to which religious Violence	Agree	Disagree
Religion can be used as a means of fabrication on Facebook	86%	14%
Facebook can create religious conflict among	86%	14%
Facebook can affect religious beliefs	84%	16%
can be fabricated on Facebook against different religious groups or societies/sects.	93%	7%
Mitigating the fabrication of can assist individuals or society at large against religious Violence.	83%	17%

Table 6 presents the statistical analyses of ethnic/tribal conflict as a factor that influences fabrication on social media platforms. The Table indicates that the majority of the respondent (95%) agreed that Ethnic Conflict could affect fabrication of on Facebook, having a negligible percentage of (5%) that disagree and also the majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that on Facebook could initiate ethnic conflict of different tribes or society with just (10%) disagree responses. (89%) Responses agreed that Facebook could increase ethnic conflict between some tribal individuals or society, with just (11%) response. Also 89%

respondents agreed that Facebook could be used against some ethnic groups of different tribes, and (11%). On the issue of mitigating the fabrication on Facebook, can assist individuals or society against ethnic conflict 82% respondents agreed, while (18%) respondents disagreed. In this section, all the areas agree or have a positive score higher than any other area due to the level of severity of the ethnic/tribal conflict, as it's a severe and current issue in the country or the whole world at large.

Table 6: Ethnic/Tribal Conflict as a Factor

Please indicate the extent to which ethnic/tribal conflict	Agree	Disagree
Ethnic conflict can influence the fabrication on Facebook	95%	5%
on Facebook, can initiate ethnic conflict among different tribes.	90%	10%
on Facebook, ethnic conflict can increase ethnic conflict between some tribal individuals or society.	89%	11%
Facebook can be used against some ethnic groups of different tribes	89%	11%
Mitigating the fabrication on Facebook can assist individuals or society against ethnic conflict.	82%	18%

Table 7: Entertainment as a factor that influences fabrication on social media platforms. The Table presents the statistical analysis of entertainment as a factor that influences the fabrication on the Facebook social media platform, with (81%) agreed responses on entertainment can influence fabrication of on Facebook, and (19%) disagree respondents. (89%) The respondents agreed that

Facebook could sometimes be funny or entertaining, while (11%) disagreed. On Facebook, jokes got (80%) agree responses while disagree responses got (20%); also, (81%) of the respondents agreed that it can be fabricated on Facebook against some innocent individuals or society just to laugh at them or create fun. In comparison 19% respondents disagree. Mitigating

the fabrication on Facebook can assist some individuals or society at large against unnecessary jokes that can harm them (90%)

agree with responses. In comparison, only (10%) disagree, which clearly shows that it could help.

Table 7: Entertainments as a factor

Please indicate the extent to which entertainment	Agree	Disagree
Entertainment can influence fabrication on Facebook	81%	19%
Facebook can sometimes be funny or entertaining	89%	11%
Facebook can increase fun and jokes	80%	20%
can be fabricated on Facebook against some innocent individuals, or society can laugh at them, or create fun.	81%	19%
It is mitigating the fabrication of assisting some individuals or society at large against unnecessary jokes that can harm them.	90%	10%

Summary of Findings

The descriptive analysis of the profiles the statistical analysis of the basic understanding of, and the statistical analysis of the factors influencing fabrication on the Facebook social media platform were carried out successfully, and the respondents have done justice to the questions and the questionnaire as a whole. The descriptive analysis of the respondents' profiles shows that the respondents were fully matured at 18 years (51%) and 30 years (42%), and also very educated as BSC/HND (48%), (25%), and PG/Masters (24%); as such, the questionnaire was well answered. On the statistical analysis of the basic understanding of, which can be passed through Facebook, got the highest response of (96%). That can be used on Facebook as a weapon got (90%) response, which might ascertain that it can be used on Facebook. The statistical analysis of the factors influencing fabrication of on the social media platform, specifically Facebook, indicates that the proposed five (5) factors influencing fabrication of on social media platform were all valid; among which are political Attitude with (94%) agree responses; financial Gain with (87%) agree responses, religious Violence with (86%) agree responses; ethnic/tribal conflict with (95%) and entertainments with (81%) agree on responses. All the responses here were above (80%), which can signify the majority; the ones with a higher percentage were political Attitude and ethnic/tribal Conflict (94% & 95%), respectively, which indicate the level of severity of the two factors. In a nutshell, the answers to the research questions can now be deduced from the research survey findings.

4.Conclusion

Currently, the Facebook social media platform is among the most popular social media platforms, with an outstanding feature to accommodate any type of news. There appears to be a lack of theory that sufficiently explains the realization of basic factors that influence the use of media platforms. Identifying factors that influence Facebook social media platforms is the focus of this research. For instance, it can be weaponized on Facebook, and you may not understand that of that. The findings of this project can categorically understand the specific factors that influence such. Another essential contribution of this research realization of how to spot, and also, the recommendations provided are as well as contributions to consider.

Theoretical Contribution: -The main goal of this research was to identify factors influencing the use of the Facebook social media platform. This research achieved that by developing proposed test models for factors affecting media platforms. The factors influencing the weaponization on Facebook social media platforms were validated by obtaining data fit for the proposed model. While the proposed model establishes each factor's features and constructs, the structural model establishes the strength of the relationship between these factors and the dependent constructs. Identifying the factors that contributed to addressing the research when studying the use of Facebook social media. The validated factors can be used for future refinement by other researchers who wish to validate these factors further. Overall, the factors were used to create a reliable instrument for

assessing the degree of weaponization on the Facebook social media platform.

Empirical Contribution: This research provides empirical (or rather statistical) evidence regarding the relationship between the factors influencing the use of Facebook social media. These factors and their dependent constructs were initially identified from the prior studies, and further using a quantitative approach (questionnaire research approach) was an excellent means of gathering data from users of different backgrounds, different locality, different religious beliefs, and various ethnic/tribal. Also, sampling was used in selecting the respondents for the questionnaire filling.

Research Implications: This research identified the fundamental factors that influence the use of the Facebook social media platform models from a comprehensive quantitative analysis of empirical studies that examine Facebook from different perspectives.

5.Recommendations

Having undergone a thorough research study and survey on the Facebook social media platform, the following recommendations are provided: -

- The general public should take it seriously and start learning and teaching themselves about it on Facebook.
- Social media platforms should create a robust algorithm that can detect and counter it immediately.
- The social media platform should also make unlimited easy access and allow individuals to flag any content by individuals and take serious action against the account holder.
- As recommended by the former INEC chairman, the government should review some of the regulations to make stiffer rules for implementation to curb.
- The government should create serious punishment and make the punishment known to the general public for whoever tries to use Facebook social media.
- The government should also create a curriculum on or insert it into another for individuals to understand the term on the Facebook social media platform.
- Security agencies should create a department that will solely dedicate work to figuring out weaponized content on Facebook social media

and always have men on the ground who can act fast.

- Media houses should have a verifiable system ready and make sure they verify any news that comes to them before publishing
- Media houses should also assign some of their members to monitor Facebook pages to avoid using their published news in other ways.
- Social media platforms should use high, current, robust technologies, government agencies, security agencies, and media houses to avoid hacking into their system.

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